

An alternative scheme for the GIS processing

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GAIA-LL-059 (V1, 21 April 2005)

ABSTRACT. An alternative scheme for the GIS processing is described, in which the global iteration is performed only on two major blocks: centroiding and source updating (S), which is performed source-wise (according to HTM region), and a calibration-attitude-global parameters update (CAG), which is performed roughly in sequence of observation time or observation batches (e.g., one batch per day). Identification of outliers and sources that are not well-behaved is entirely done during the source processing, thus eliminating the need for internal iteration of the CAG processes. This scheme should allow a considerable reduction, compared with the GDAAS-1 and 2 scheme, both in computation and database access. However, it requires that the database is optimized *both* for HTM-wise and time/batch-wise data access.

1 Introduction

The current baseline approach to the Gaia core astrometric processing is the so-called Global Iterative Solution (GIS), in which several processes are executed in a cyclic sequence until convergence. The following GIS processes are normally considered:

- the source update (S), in which the astrometric parameters of an astronomical source (in the core processing, this is always a star or quasar) are determined;
- the attitude update (A), in which the celestial orientation of the instrument axes is determined as a function of time;
- the calibration update (C), in which all (geometric, photometric, and other) instrument calibrations are determined – for simplicity, each calibration datum is assumed to remain constant over a certain time interval, which may however be very different depending on the type of calibration;
- the global update (G), which takes care of any model parameters that are constant throughout the mission – from a data processing point of view, this is equivalent to a calibration on the longest time scale.

The processes must be iterated because each one of them needs data from the three other processes; on the other hand, a solution directly taking these dependencies into account stills seems out of reach by many orders of magnitude.

Similar schemes are envisaged for the core photometric and radial-velocity processing, although there is no equivalent to the attitude update in those cases.

The overall convergence of the GIS scheme as outlined above was demonstrated as part of the GDAAS study (see UB-GDAAS2-TN-023). However, that study showed even more clearly the need to design the GIS scheme more cleverly in order to streamline database access and avoid unnecessary repetition of complex calculations.

As the instrument model becomes more sophisticated, it is necessary to involve more dependencies and types of calibration in this scheme. For example, calibration of the chromaticity and subsequent correction for the effect requires that photometric information is included, or at least the broad-band photometry. This then requires a photometric calibration to be carried out in parallel with the core astrometry. Similarly, the photometric processing and astrometric centroiding on the raw CCD samples requires that the line-spread function (LSF) is known, which leads to a calibration process in which both photometric and astrometric information is needed, and which therefore must be part of the overall iteration scheme. A related problem is that all calibrations as well as the attitude determination can only use so-called ‘well-behaved’ stars (apparently single, non-variable and otherwise non-problematic), and the process to define this subset of sources must also be iterated, since progressively sharper criteria must be applied as the GIS converges. The source matching and the general treatment of outliers should be considered in the same iterative context. Thus, much of the so-called ‘initial data treatment’ (IDT) cannot be performed just once but must be brought into the global iteration scheme.

The GIS scheme described below is intended to provide a better structure for including these several improvements that will be necessary in GDAAS-3 and subsequent developments aiming towards a complete data processing system.

2 Parallel processing of CAG

The attitude updating is supposed to be done in batches covering a few spin periods of the satellite. However, in principle these attitude intervals could be made as long as one wishes; the limitation is only that a longer interval requires a bigger data array to be carried along before the attitude parameters can be solved. Each attitude interval can be solved independently of other such intervals; a weakness at the ends of the intervals can be avoided by using slightly overlapping intervals followed by interpolation of the results. (A more elegant solution to this problem can probably be found.)

The calibration updating is also done independently for subsequent time intervals. Here, however, the length of the interval is determined by a compromise between statistical errors and modelisation errors: too short an interval will contain too few observations for a statistically valid calibration, while too long an interval entails a risk that the instrument changes significantly over the interval. The optimum calibration interval depends on the type of calibration considered; in particular, parameters describing geometric or photometric variations on a large spatial scale are expected to change on a shorter time scale than variations on a small spatial scale. There is no need at the moment to specify the exact time intervals required for the various calibrations; for the moment we might think in terms of three widely different time scales, referred to as ‘short’ (of order one day), ‘medium’ (of order several weeks or even months) and ‘long’ (of order years or perhaps the whole mission).

FIGURE 1: Schematic illustration of the parallel processing of data for the calibration, attitude determination, and global parameter determination (CAG). The raw and elementary data are run through, roughly in the sequence in which they were observed, while accumulating the various data arrays. At specific instants the relevant parameters are computed from a data array, which is then immediately re-initialized. The memory storage needed for the totality of data arrays remains constant.

Global updating refers to quantities of a truly global (and constant) nature, such as the PPN parameter γ and the components of the galactocentric acceleration of the solar system. However, from the viewpoint of data processing, it is equivalent to a calibration updating on the longest possible time scale, i.e., the duration of the mission.

In a similar way, the attitude update can be regarded as a kind of calibration on a short time scale.

The three GIS processes CAG share the property that the accumulation of the least-squares (normal) equations for their solution can be performed in time sequence, following the order in which the observations were taken (although some scrambling of the observations on the shortest time scale would not matter). At the end of the relevant interval, all necessary data have been accumulated and the equations can then be solved to provide the updating of the relevant subset of (attitude, calibration or global) parameters. Immediately after this solution, the memory used for storing the equations can be released, and a new data array initialized for the next interval (Fig. 1).

Furthermore, all three processes basically need access to the same kind of data, namely the field angle residuals (observed *minus* computed field angles), which therefore only have to be computed once for all of them, or retrieved only once from the database. (It is a bit more complicated for the calibration of the LSF, which requires access to the raw data, but the principle remains the same.)

It is therefore natural to run the three processes strictly parallel, so that a given observation (or residual, or raw data) is read only once and used concurrently by all three processes.

3 Badly-behaved stars and outlier treatment

The attitude, calibration and global parameter updates should only use ‘well-behaved’ stars, i.e., without any sign of duplicity or variability, and even for the well-behaved stars we need a filter against the occasional outlier. Previously no clear criteria have been set up for how to create such a clean data set. Bad observations may produce large residuals in any of the fitting processes, and the original idea (e.g., in GAIA-LL-034) was to make each process robust against outliers. This was indeed implemented in GDAAS-1, leading to a large number of internal iterations in each process.

Here I propose a major change of philosophy. It is obvious that duplicity and variability are most clearly and robustly detected in the processes where the data can be directly tested against the null hypothesis that the star is well-behaved. This is the case in the source updating for the astrometry and photometry, where the centroid position and source intensity are tested against a model with five astrometric parameters and constant intensity, respectively, and in the centroiding process where the raw data are tested against the calibrated LSF. It is in these processes that we can most easily identify not only the badly-behaved sources, but also the individual data points that may be considered as outliers in *all* the processes.

The most recent version of the astrometric source updating (GAIA-LL-055, UB-GDAAS2-TN-026) was designed to cope with outliers, adjust the overall weight system, etc., in a very efficient and robust way, at least compared with the previous algorithm. Essentially this was achieved by performing the internal iterations completely inside the algorithm, and using a stable adaptive weight control. The results – the unit weight error per source and the weight factors for individual observations – can be used to identify badly-behaved sources and outliers.

The very important practical consequence of these considerations is that no internal iterations are needed in the CAG processes. In fact this is a prerequisite for the CAG processing as outlined in Sect. 2, since it is not possible to iterate any of these processes without either keeping all the observation equations in memory during an accumulation interval, or returning to the beginning of the interval, reading the data again. The first option is clearly unfeasible at least for the longer (calibration and global updating) intervals, while the second option would increase the processing time unacceptably.

4 Source processing

The source processing has a radically different data access pattern than the CAG processing. Here it is sufficient to treat one source at a time, or more generally the sources or detections referred to a specific sky area (e.g., HTM region). To fit into the new GIS scheme it may be desirable to widen the source processing concept by including:

1. the centroiding and flux determination (they use the same LSF fitting algorithm);
2. the astrometric source updating;
3. the photometric source updating;

4. and perhaps (one mode of) the cross-matching algorithm, viz., the improved cross-matching that should be performed after some GIS iterations.

These processes can all be run by sky area, and they are all needed to identify badly-behaved stars and outliers: (1) identifies resolved or partially resolved double stars; (2) identifies astrometric binaries and similar; (3) identifies variable stars; an (4) may sort out some of the problem cases, e.g., high-proper-motion stars.

5 Global iterations

With the C, A and G processes running concurrently, the GIS iteration reduces to alternately running the source processing S and the CAG block. Thus the question of the order in which the GIS processes should be run has been eliminated.

A remaining problem is however to design a bootstrap processing that quickly brings the data (in particular attitude and calibration) into the linear (sub-arcsec) region, from which GIS (including source matching) can converge rapidly. Such a special initial processing is required in view of the large (~ 20 arcsec) uncertainty of the absolute satellite pointing from the on-board attitude. It will probably use only a subset of the brighter stars for which good *a priori* positions are known, and could be part of the first-look processing.

6 Some practical considerations

6.1 Size of data arrays for the CAG processing

The CAG processing illustrated in Fig. 1 requires that the normal equations for the various attitude, calibration and global updates are carried along in memory for the whole accumulation interval. Is this realistic?

To get a feeling for the required memory size, Table 1 gives a first-order estimation of the data arrays needed for the various Astro calibrations. Explanation to some of the columns:

- N_{FOV} is the number of Astro fields for which a *separate* calibration is needed. All large-scale effects except CTI are expected to require separate calibrations for the two viewing directions.
- N_{CCD} is the number of CCDs considered in the Gaia-2 design. Note that ASM and BBP are included everywhere except for the chromaticity.
- N_{elem} stands for the number of elements in which a CCD is divided. Following GAIA-ARI-BAS-011 it is assumed that 3 elements are needed for the large-scale geometric distortion, e.g., in the form of three orthogonal polynomials in the transverse coordinate. The same is assumed for the photometric large-scale calibration. For the small-scale effects, N_{elem} is taken to be the number of columns per CCD. In either case the elements are treated as independent entities to be calibrated (thus the assumption of orthogonality if polynomials are used).

TABLE 1: Estimation of the number of parameters (N_{par}) needed for the calibration of the Astro instruments, and the size S (in reals) of the corresponding data arrays. See text for an explanation of other columns. The table gives the *instantaneous* values, i.e., the number of parameters and array sizes in use at a given time; summed over the whole mission the total number of calibration parameters may be many times higher.

Type	Time scale	N_{FOV}	N_{CCD}	N_{elem}	N_{func}	N_{term}	N_{par}	S
<i>Large-Scale Calibrations:</i>								
Photometric	short	2	170	3	1020	6	6120	30600
Chromaticity	medium	2	110	1	220	5	1100	5060
Geometric AL	short	2	170	3	1020	1	1020	4080
Geometric AC	medium	2	170	3	1020	1	1020	4080
LSF AL	medium	2	170	1	340	110	37400	2114120
LSF AC	long	2	170	1	340	110	37400	2114120
CTI AL	short	1	180	1	180	10	1800	12240
CTI AC	short	1	180	1	180	10	1800	12240
<i>Small-Scale Calibrations:</i>								
Photometric	medium	1	180	1966	353880	6	2123280	10616400
Geometric AL	medium	1	180	1966	353880	1	353880	1769400
Geometric AC	long	1	180	1966	353880	1	353880	1769400
CTI AL	medium	1	180	1966	353880	1	353880	1769400
All	any				1419840		3272580	20221140

- $N_{\text{func}} = N_{\text{FOV}}N_{\text{CCD}}N_{\text{elem}}$ is the total the number of independent functions describing the calibration at a given time.
- N_{term} is the number of independent variables defining the function. This equals the number of photometric bands (5 or 6) for the photometric and chromaticity calibrations; for the LSF it is the number of photometric bands (5) times the number of parameters needed to describe each quasi-monochromatic LSF (22 according to UB-GDAAS2-TN-021). For the CTI it is arbitrarily estimated to be of order 10.
- $N_{\text{par}} = N_{\text{func}}N_{\text{term}}$ is the total number of calibration parameters for the calibration at a given time.
- $S = N_{\text{func}}(N_{\text{term}}(N_{\text{term}} + 1)/2 + N_{\text{term}} + 3)$ is the estimated size (in reals) of the data array needed to store the normal equations and auxiliary statistics. This assumes that N_{func} independent least-squares solutions must be computed, each with N_{term} unknowns. (The normal equations for m unknown requires $m(m + 1)/2 + m$ reals.) The 3 extra reals per function are for the auxiliary statistics, e.g., the number of observations, their total weight, and the sum of the squared normalized residuals.

The total memory needed to store all concurrent data arrays is therefore of order 160 MB (assuming 8 bytes per real), which does not seem excessive. The data arrays for the attitude and global updates are very modest by comparison.

6.2 Data access patterns

A critical aspect of the proposed scheme is that the data (both raw CCD samples and elementary data) need to be accessed in two different ways: either by object or region on the sky, or by observation time. The time-wise access need not be strictly in order of observing time, but could be in bigger chunks corresponding to time intervals up to the length of the shortest attitude or calibration interval (~ 1 day). In the HTM structure, these data are of course stored along a band (up to ~ 5 deg width) along a great circle, but only a fraction of the data in that band would be asked for.

It is probably necessary for *any* efficient implementation of the Gaia core processing to be able to access the data in these two complementary ways. Very high priority should therefore be given to finding a very efficient way to achieve this.